

Modeling the effect of non-linear distortion in a Centralized RAN with analog optical fronthaul

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Abstract—The Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture has potential to achieve the target goals that have been set for 5G. However, as the number of radio signals to be transported from the Centralized Base Station (CBS) to the distributed Remote Antenna Units (RAUs) grows, the use of contemporary *digital* fronthaul technologies (such as CPRI) complicates. One simple way to address this problem consists in multiplexing the baseband signals intended to the different RAUs in the frequency domain and, after that, use the resulting *analog* signal to modulate the intensity of the optical carrier. This way, there is no bandwidth expansion and the processing delay is kept low; however, as the *ideal* fronthaul assumption does not hold any more in this case, the impairments that the analog optical fronthaul introduces should be taken into account when performing the digital signal processing in transmission. In this paper, we focus on the non-linear distortion that the external Mach-Zehnder (optical) modulator introduces and, through it, estimate the End-to-End (E2E) performance when different intensity modulation indexes (or clipping ratios) are used. As expected, moderate levels of non-linear distortion are beneficial if properly selected according to the C-RAN configuration.

I. INTRODUCTION

Next generation (5G) mobile networks will have to support about 1000 times higher data rate per unit area, 10-100 times more data traffic per user, 10-1000 times higher number of devices, 10 times longer battery life, and 5 times less End-to-End (E2E) latency than today (4G) [1]. The current trend to address these challenges consists in separating the *digital* baseband processing and the *analog* radio processing into two parts, implementing the so-called Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture [2]. A critical part of this architecture is the fronthaul network, which connects the Centralized Base Station (CBS) with the distributed Remote Antenna Units (RAUs) using optical fibers. So far, contemporary fronthaul technologies have been designed to introduce negligible distortion in the radio signal that is transported. For example, the Common Public Radio Interface (CPRI) standard achieves this goal digitalizing the analog (I-Q) baseband signals that the CBS generates [3]. However, the bandwidth expansion incurred in this digitalization process, as well as the delay processing that is introduced and the cost of the hardware that is needed [4], makes CPRI not suitable for ultra-dense deployments of small cells using a C-RAN architecture.

The transportation of the analog baseband signals directly over the optical fiber does not suffer from the scalability problem that digital fronthaul solutions have (*i.e.*, bandwidth expansion, processing delay, and RAU hardware complexity).

However, the main challenges that these analog Radio-over-Fiber (RoF) solutions have is the non-linear distortion that the different optical/electrical components of the fronthaul introduce. The simplest way to address this problem consists in limiting the dynamic range of the radio signal [5], [6], such that there is a very low probability of having an instantaneous power peak outside the linear response region of the fronthaul. However, such an approach is not sensible in practice, as the Optical Signal-to-Noise Ratio (OSNR), as well as the received SNR of the hybrid optical-wireless link of the C-RAN, are notably affected when the intensity modulation index of the fronthaul is just selected to minimize non-linear distortion [7].

In the *analog* fronthaul solution that we propose, the passband radio signals intended to the different RAUs are placed on different Intermediate Frequencies (IFs) [8]. Then, the aggregated radio signal that results is used to modulate the intensity of the optical carrier using an external Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM). A Passive Optical Network (PON), like the ones that exist today in most urban centers to provide Fiber-to-the-Home (FTTH), is used to connect the CBS with the distributed RAUs [9]. At the RAU, only analog signal processing is implemented to detect, filter, and up-convert the passband IF signal onto the RF portion of the spectrum in which it is transmitted over-the-air. In this paper, the effect of the non-linear distortion that the MZM introduces is modeled theoretically using the Busgang theorem as in [10]. Thanks to this approach, it is possible to evaluate the impact that the non-linear distortion has on the E2E performance of the C-RAN and, through it, select the most convenient set of parameters to configure the analog fronthaul transmission (*i.e.*, optical modulation index and clipping ratio of the radio signal).

The non-linear distortion that the RoF link introduces has been studied in [11] and [12], and references therein, in presence of both single- and multi-carrier signals. However, in most of these cases, the Laser Diode (LD) that feeds the optical fiber is *directly* modulated with the radio signal to be transmitted, and the performance is usually evaluated using experimental measurements and simulations. Apart from clipping, other Peak-to-Average Power Ratio (PAPR) reduction techniques [5] can be applied to minimize the effect of non-linear distortion. Nevertheless, these techniques should be implemented after the OFDM carriers are combined together, since a PAPR re-growth effect takes place when multiple signals are transported over the same optical link [12].

Fig. 1. Illustration of the proposed C-RAN architecture comprised of a CBS, a single-fiber passive optical *fronthaul* network, and M RAUs. All the digital signal processing is performed at the CBS. Optical fronthaul and RAUs contain only analog hardware to keep latency and cost low. Simultaneous transmission of the radio signals over the fronthaul to the distributed RAUs is done over different IFs of the electrical spectrum. Cyclic Prefix is omitted for simplicity. S/P = Serial-to-Parallel; P/S = Parallel-to-Serial; D/A = Digital-to-Analog; MZM = Mach-Zehnder Modulator; PD = Photodetector; PA = Power Amplifier.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the system model and derives the signal model for the different parts of the optical (fiber) and wireless (radio) transmission. Section III characterizes the impact of the MZM non-linear distortion in the received radio signal, and derives closed form expressions that model this impairment. Simulation results that estimate the E2E performance of the C-RAN for different configuration parameters are presented in Section IV. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section V.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The simplified system model of the proposed C-RAN architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1. The system contains a CBS, a large number of distributed RAUs, and a tree-like PON that connects the CBS with the distributed RAUs using a Single-Mode Fiber (SMF) with passive optical splitters. Bidirectional connectivity between CBS and the M RAUs is achieved using different wavelengths (*i.e.*, λ_1 for downstream and λ_2 for upstream). As this paper focuses on the downstream, we assume that the optical communication takes place in the middle windows of the SMF (*i.e.*, $\lambda_1 \approx 1500$ nm). This is because the fiber attenuation is lower there, and the downstream (point-to-multipoint) communication is more power limited than the upstream (multipoint-to-point) counterpart.

A. Signal processing at the Centralized Base Station

The incoming bit streams intended to the different RAUs are first grouped into symbols and, after that, mapped into the corresponding M -QAM constellation points. The symbol block $\{X_{m,i}[k]\}_{k=0}^{N-1}$ that RAU m transmits on time interval i is then modulated onto the subcarriers of the OFDM signal using an N -size Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) block, such that the samples of the complex time domain signal are

$$x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}[n] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_{m,i}[k] \exp\left(j \frac{2\pi kn}{N}\right) \quad n = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (1)$$

To keep the notation simple, the Cyclic Prefix (CP) addition in transmission and removal in reception is not considered.

After that, the resulting time domain samples $\{x_{m,i}[n]\}_{n=0}^{N-1}$ are fed into a Digital-to-Analog (D/A) converter that generates the complex continuous (analog) time domain signal

$$x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} X_{m,i}[k] g(t - iT_s) \exp\left(j \frac{2\pi kt}{T_s}\right), \quad (2)$$

where T_s is the OFDM symbol time and $g(t)$ is the response of the pulse shape filter. Note that in baseline OFDM, $g(t)$ is a rectangular pulse of height one and time width T_s .

The transmission of the M OFDM carriers over the same optical fronthaul is achieved using Frequency Division Multiple Access (FDMA). That is, the complex baseband signal in (2) is first upconverted to m -th IF

$$f_m = (m-1)(N/T_s) \quad m = 1, \dots, M \quad (3)$$

and, after that, are combined together to obtain

$$s_{\text{agg},i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \Re\left\{x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) \exp\left(j2\pi f_m t\right)\right\} \\ = \Re\left\{\left[\sum_{m=1}^M x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) \exp\left(j2\pi \Delta f_m t\right)\right] \exp\left(j2\pi f_{\text{IF}} t\right)\right\}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$f_{\text{IF}} = \sum_{m=1}^M f_m / M, \quad \Delta f_m = f_m - f_{\text{IF}}, \quad (5)$$

are the mean IF of the carrier-aggregated OFDM signal and the frequency offset of the m -th OFDM carrier, respectively. Then, re-arranging the terms of (4), it is possible to show that

$$s_{\text{agg}}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) = \sum_i s_{\text{agg},i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) = \sum_i a_i(t) \cos\left(2\pi f_{\text{IF}} t + \phi_i(t)\right), \quad (6)$$

where

$$a_i(t) = \left| \sum_{m=1}^M x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) \exp\left(j2\pi \Delta f_m t\right) \right|, \quad (7)$$

$$\phi_i(t) = \arg\left\{ \sum_{m=1}^M x_{m,i}^{\text{ofdm}}(t) \exp\left(j2\pi \Delta f_m t\right) \right\}, \quad (8)$$

are the instantaneous amplitude and phase of the aggregated OFDM signal. Note that the peak values of $s_{\text{agg}}^{\text{ofdm}}(t)$ are upper bounded by the values that the signal envelope $a_i(t)$ takes.

B. Transportation of the signal over the optical fronthaul

Before using (6) to modulate the intensity of the optical carrier, it must be adapted to the parameters of the external optical modulator. To achieve this goal, the input voltage applied to the control terminals of the MZM should be

$$v_{\text{agg}}(t) = V_B + \beta s_{\text{agg}}(t)(V_\pi/\pi), \quad (9)$$

where V_B and V_π are the bias and half-wave voltages of the MZM, respectively, β is the intensity modulation index, and

$$s_{\text{agg}}(t) = s_{\text{agg}}^{\text{ofdm}}(t)/\sqrt{\mathbb{E}\{|s_{\text{agg}}^{\text{ofdm}}(t)|^2\}} \quad (10)$$

is a scaled version of the aggregated OFDM signal that has unitary power. The specific choice of β controls the range over which the MZM works most of the time and, as it will be shown later, the level of non-linear distortion power that is introduced in the transmitted radio signals.

Let P_o denote the average optical power that the LD that feeds the MZM generates. Then, based on the MZM transfer function, it is possible to see that the *envelope* of the intensity of the optical carrier at the MZM output is

$$\begin{aligned} |p_o(t)| &= \frac{P_o}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{V_\pi} v_{\text{agg}}(t) \right) \right] \\ &= \frac{P_o}{2} \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\pi V_B}{V_\pi} + \beta s_{\text{agg}}(t) \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

When an appropriate bias point is used, such as $V_B = 3V_\pi/2$, the envelope of the optical carrier intensity becomes

$$|p_o(t)| = \frac{P_o}{2} \left[1 + \sin(\beta s_{\text{agg}}(t)) \right] \approx \frac{P_o}{2} \left[1 + \beta s_{\text{agg}}(t) \right] \quad \beta \ll 1. \quad (12)$$

Let ω_o represent the angular frequency of the optical carrier that the LD generates (with $\omega_o \gg \omega_m$). Then, the optical signal intensity at the output of the MZM is given by

$$\begin{aligned} p_o(t) &= \Re\{|p_o(t)| \exp(j\omega_o t)\} \\ &= (P_o/2) [1 + \sin(\beta s_{\text{agg}}(t))] \cos(\omega_o t), \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $(P_o/2) \cos(\omega_o t)$ denotes the unmodulated optical carrier that is transmitted with the optical aggregated OFDM signal. The effect of chromatic dispersion is minimal in this fronthaul architecture; therefore, no optical carrier suppression is needed in the CBS to control this transmission impairment.

C. Signal processing at the Remote Antenna Units

The optical signal that illuminates the Photodetector (PD) in the RAU generates an electrical current that is equal to

$$i_D(t) = \mu \frac{|p_o(t)|}{L_f L_s} = \frac{\mu}{L_f L_s} \left[\frac{P_o}{2} + \frac{P_o}{2} \sin(\beta s_{\text{agg}}(t)) \right], \quad (14)$$

where μ [A/W] is the PD responsivity, L_f is the optical fiber attenuation, and L_s is the loss of the power splitters. The detected current can be divided into two terms, *i.e.*,

$$i_D(t) = I_D + i_d(t), \quad (15)$$

where the first term

$$I_D = \mathbb{E}\{i_D(t)\} = \frac{\mu P_o}{2 L_f L_s} \quad (16)$$

is the DC component that remains constant for all intensity modulation indexes and input signals, and the second term

$$i_d(t) = i_D(t) - I_D = I_D \sin(\beta s_{\text{agg}}(t)) \quad (17)$$

is the AC component that depends on the instantaneous value of the aggregated OFDM signal. Since the response of the MZM is not linear, it is possible to apply Bussgang theorem and model (17) as the sum of two new signals, *i.e.*,

$$i_d(t) = i_s(t) + i_w(t), \quad (18)$$

where

$$i_s(t) = \alpha [I_D s_{\text{agg}}(t)] \quad 0 \leq \alpha \leq 1 \quad (19)$$

is a scaled version of the original aggregated OFDM signal and $i_w(t)$ represents the non-linear distortion noise that is added. In practice, the Signal-to-Distortion Ratio (SDR) of the signal in (18) depends on the modulation index β , as well as the clipping threshold that is used in the aggregated OFDM signal.

Let us assume that the electrical bandwidth of the aggregated OFDM signal (B_{agg}) can be accommodated into the electrical modulation bandwidth of the LD ($B_{e,\text{ld}}$), *i.e.*,

$$B_{e,\text{ld}} \cong B_{\text{agg}} = M(N\Delta f) \quad \Delta f = 1/T_s, \quad (20)$$

and that the optical responses of the LD, PON, and PD are flat in frequency. Then, the OSNR at the PD input becomes

$$\text{OSNR} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|i_d(t)|^2\}}{\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}}, \quad (21)$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{shot}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{th}}(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{rin}}(t)|^2\} \quad (22)$$

includes all sources of noise that are added in the optical fronthaul [7]. The shot noise power, which arises from the random nature of the photons collected by the PD, is given by

$$\mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{shot}}(t)|^2\} = 2q I_D B_{\text{agg}}, \quad (23)$$

where q is the electron charge. Note that unless the mean optical power changes, the shot noise power remains constant for all modulation indexes β . The thermal noise power is

$$\mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{th}}(t)|^2\} = 4F k_B T_o B_{\text{agg}}/R_L, \quad (24)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, F is the noise factor of the RAU amplifier, T_o is the absolute temperature, and R_L is the load resistance. Finally, the Relative Intensity Noise (RIN), which is originated by the fluctuations in the optical intensity due to the random nature of the LD stimulated emissions, is

$$\mathbb{E}\{|i_{\text{rin}}(t)|^2\} = \text{RIN} I_D^2 B_{\text{agg}}, \quad (25)$$

where RIN [dB/Hz] is specified for the LD that is selected.

Finally, the electrical signal that is obtained at the output of the PD is passband-filtered, up-converted to the RF band, and amplified before its transmission into the wireless channel.

D. Signal processing at the Mobile Station

The wireless channel of the small cell network attenuates the radio signal and adds co-channel interference plus Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN). Due to that, the SNR that the Mobile Station (MS) experiences in reception is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SNR} &= \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|i_s(t)|^2\} \left(\frac{G_{\text{rau}}}{L_w}\right)^2}{\left[\mathbb{E}\{|i_w(t)|^2\} + \mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}\right] \left(\frac{G_{\text{rau}}}{L_w}\right)^2 + \mathbb{E}\{|n_w(t)|^2\}} \\ &= \text{OSNR} \times \left[\frac{1 - \mathbb{E}\{|i_w(t)|^2\} / \mathbb{E}\{|i_d(t)|^2\}}{1 + \mathbb{E}\{|i_w(t)|^2\} / \mathbb{E}\{|n_o(t)|^2\}} \right] \\ &\times \left[1 + \mathbb{E}\{|n_w(t)|^2\} (L_w / G_{\text{rau}})^2 \right]^{-1}, \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where G_{rau} is the gain of the RAU Power Amplifier (PA) and L_w is the path loss attenuation of the wireless link. If directive antennas are used at the RAU and/or MS, the corresponding antenna gain(s) should be included in G_{rau} . For any additional losses in the transmission chain, its effect should be considered in L_w . Moreover, since the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT)

$$Y_m[k] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} y_m[n] \exp\left(-j \frac{2\pi kn}{N}\right) \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1. \quad (27)$$

is applied to demodulate the OFDM signal in the MS, the power of any signal clipping and non-linear distortion that is generated in the optical fronthaul can be evenly distributed among the N subcarriers of each of the M OFDM signals.

III. EFFECT OF FRONTHAUL NON-LINEARITY IN THE SNR

According to (12), the MZM transfer function becomes linear as the modulation index $\beta \rightarrow 0$. In this situation, the non-linear distortion power is reduced and, in the limit, the received SNR in (26) is maximized (for a given OSNR). Nevertheless, such working regime is not attractive in practice as the actual OSNR in the optical fronthaul is also affected by the value that β takes, as shown when combining (17) and (21). Therefore, some non-linear distortion may be beneficial if the OSNR improvement that is obtained outperforms the impact of distortion on the received SNR. The optimization of β for a given optical fronthaul configuration is now studied in detail.

A. Theoretical model for the non-linear distortion

For a large number of subcarriers (*e.g.*, $N \geq 64$), an OFDM time domain signal can be approximated by a set of independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.) Gaussian Random Variables (RVs) [13]. According to the Busgang theorem, non-linear distortion in an OFDM-based system can be described with a gain factor and an additional noise component [10]. In other words, let X be a zero-mean Gaussian RV and $g(\cdot)$ an arbitrary memoryless distortion on X ; then,

$$g(X) = \alpha X + Y \quad \text{with} \quad \mathbb{E}\{XY\} = 0. \quad (28)$$

In the previous equation, the gain factor

$$\alpha = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{X g(X)\}}{\sigma_X^2} \quad (29)$$

is constant and the noise component Y that is added is not correlated with the value that the input RV X takes. When the

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the non-linear distortions that the aggregated OFDM signal experiences when transported over the optical fronthaul. Continuous time signals are replaced by their discrete versions with oversampling factor L .

FFT is applied in reception, the noise Y is transformed into AWGN in the frequency domain due to the central limit theorem. Therefore, the time domain average $\mathbb{E}\{g(X)\} = \mathbb{E}\{Y\}$ contributes only to the value of the DC subcarrier, whereas an additional zero-mean AWGN component with variance

$$\sigma_Y^2 = \mathbb{E}\{Y^2\} - \mathbb{E}\{Y\}^2, \quad (30)$$

and second moment

$$\mathbb{E}\{Y^2\} = \mathbb{E}\{g^2(X)\} - \alpha^2 \sigma_X^2 \quad (31)$$

is added on the modulated subcarriers, where σ_X^2 is the variance of RV X . To sum up, the overall effect of the non-linearity $g(\cdot)$ is an increase of the AWGN power by σ_Y^2 and a decrease in the useful signal power by a factor α^2 .

B. Signal clipping and MZM non-linearity

The simplest way to limit the extreme values of the aggregated OFDM signal consists in clipping its amplitude peaks and, after that, use the resulting signal to modulate the intensity of the optical carrier [5]. For few OFDM carriers (*i.e.*, low M), where the complete generation of the aggregated OFDM signal is possible in the digital domain, clipping can be performed before the D/A conversion. However, since the number of OFDM carriers that share the same optical fronthaul in our system model is large (*i.e.*, the PON splitting factor can be as high as 1:64), it is more reasonable in our case to perform both signal aggregation and clipping in the analog domain.

In order to study the impact of clipping, we need to characterize the probability of an amplitude peak event. In case of a continuous time signal, the amplitude peaks can be computed by setting the signal derivative to zero. However, this operation is not trivial as the determination of the roots of a function composed by the sum of sine waves is difficult [14]. One simple way to overcome this problem consists in replacing the continuous time signal $s_{\text{agg}}(t)$ by its samples $s_{\text{agg}}[n]$ taken at a given oversampling factor L , as illustrated in Fig. 2. Then, by studying the effect of the optical fronthaul in the discrete time domain, we can approximate the actual effect of the non-linear distortion in the continuous time signals as accurately as desired (*i.e.*, by selecting a proper L).

Let A_{max} be the clipping level of the input signal. Then, the clipping operation can be mathematically written as

$$\tilde{s}_{\text{agg}}[n] = \begin{cases} A_{\text{max}} & s_{\text{agg}}[n] > A_{\text{max}} \\ s_{\text{agg}}[n] & |s_{\text{agg}}[n]| \leq A_{\text{max}} \\ -A_{\text{max}} & s_{\text{agg}}[n] < -A_{\text{max}} \end{cases}, \quad (32)$$

TABLE I
OPTICAL FRONTHAUL PARAMETERS

Symbol	Description	Value [unit]
P_o	LD mean optical power	5 [dBm]
L_f	Optical fiber loss	0.3 [dB/km]
L_s	PON splitting loss	1:16, 1:32, 1:64
d_o	Optical fiber length	20 [km]
μ	Photodetector responsivity	0.75 [A/W]
T_o	Optical receiver temperature	275 [K]
R_L	Receiver load resistance	50 [Ω]
RIN	Relative Intensity Noise parameter	-155 [dB/Hz]
B	Bandwidth of each OFDM carrier	20 [MHz]
G	RF power amplifier (RAU)	20 [dB]
F	Receiver amplifier noise factor (RAU)	1 [dB]

where the Clipping Ratio (CR) in logarithmic scale, *i.e.*,

$$\text{CR [dB]} = 20 \log_{10}(A_{\max}/\sigma_s), \quad (33)$$

depends on the clipping threshold (A_{\max}) and the standard deviation of the aggregated OFDM signal (σ_s). Similarly, the intensity of the optical signal at the MZM output becomes

$$g(s_{\text{agg}}[n]) = \sin(\beta \tilde{s}_{\text{agg}}[n]). \quad (34)$$

Now, we are ready to derive the closed form expressions that correspond for the gain factor in (29) and the additional noise variance in (30) when modeling the non-linear distortion.

C. Closed form expressions for the gain factor α

To determine the gain factor that scales the input signal in Fig. 2, we first need to compute the cross correlation between the input and output signals, which can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{Xg(X)\} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} x g(x) f_X(x) dx \\ &= 2 \int_{A_{\max}/\beta}^{\infty} x \sin(A_{\max}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_X^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &+ 2 \int_0^{A_{\max}/\beta} x \sin(\beta x) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_X^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi\sigma_X^2}} \sin(A_{\max}) \int_{A_{\max}/\beta}^{\infty} x \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &+ \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi\sigma_X^2}} \int_0^{A_{\max}/\beta} x \sin(\beta x) \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &= \beta \sigma_X^2 \exp\left(-\frac{\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}{2}\right) \Re\left\{\text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{\max}^2}{2\sigma_X^2 \beta^2}} + j\sqrt{\frac{\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}{2}}\right)\right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

where $\text{erf}(x + jy)$ is the complex error function [15]. Then, when combining (35) with (29), final closed form expression

$$\alpha = \beta \exp\left(-\frac{\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}{2}\right) \Re\left\{\text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{CR}}{2}} + j\sqrt{\frac{\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}{2}}\right)\right\} \quad (36)$$

results, where the CR given in (33) should be in linear scale.

D. Closed form expressions for additional noise variance σ_Y^2

The expected value of the optical fronthaul output $\mathbb{E}\{g(X)\} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g(x) f_X(x) dx$ only affects the DC sub-carrier which, in our system model, is not used to transmit

any information. However, when we focus on the rest of the subcarriers of the optical fronthaul, it is possible to see that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}\{g^2(X)\} &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} g^2(x) f_X(x) dx \\ &= 2 \int_{A_{\max}/\beta}^{\infty} \sin^2(A_{\max}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_X^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &+ 2 \int_0^{A_{\max}/\beta} \sin^2(\beta x) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_X^2}} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &= \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi\sigma_X^2}} \sin^2(A_{\max}) \int_{A_{\max}/\beta}^{\infty} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &+ \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi\sigma_X^2}} \int_0^{A_{\max}/\beta} \sin^2(\beta x) \exp\left(-\frac{x^2}{2\sigma_X^2}\right) dx \\ &= \sin^2(A_{\max}) + \left[\frac{1}{2} - \sin^2(A_{\max})\right] \text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{\max}^2}{2\sigma_X^2 \beta^2}}\right) \\ &- \frac{1}{2} \exp(-2\beta^2 \sigma_X^2) \Re\left\{\text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{A_{\max}^2}{2\sigma_X^2 \beta^2}} + j\sqrt{2\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}\right)\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

results. Then, when combining (37) with (31), the final closed form expression for the additional noise variance is obtained:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_Y^2 &= \sin^2(A_{\max}) + \left[\frac{1}{2} - \sin^2(A_{\max})\right] \text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{CR}}{2}}\right) \\ &- \frac{1}{2} \exp(-2\beta^2 \sigma_X^2) \Re\left\{\text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{CR}}{2}} + j\sqrt{2\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}\right)\right\} \\ &- \beta^2 \sigma_X^2 \exp(-\beta^2 \sigma_X^2) \Re^2\left\{\text{erf}\left(\sqrt{\frac{\text{CR}}{2}} + j\sqrt{\frac{\beta^2 \sigma_X^2}{2}}\right)\right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The optical parameters that were used to study the impact of non-linear distortion in the proposed C-RAN architecture are presented in Table I. In the wireless part of the network, a channel model with a strong specular component is used to characterize the small cell environment. That is, the path loss attenuation is estimated using the free-space path loss formula

$$L_w[\text{dB}] = 20 \log_{10}(d_w) + 20 \log_{10}(f_c) + 32.45, \quad (39)$$

where $f_c = 3.5$ [GHz] is the central frequency of the transmitted RF carriers and $d_w = 10$ [m] is the distance of the wireless link. Moreover, $\mathbb{E}\{|n_w(t)|^2\} = N_0 B$ is the variance of the AWGN that is added in the wireless channel, assuming a noise power spectral density $N_0 = -174$ [dBm/Hz].

The solid blue lines of Fig. 3 show the OSNR that each individual RAU experiences when the intensity modulation index (β) and the number of RAUs (M) in the optical fronthaul vary. As expected, the OSNR grows with β and decreases with M . It is interesting to note that these OSNR values are notably lower than the ones reported in the literature for point-to-point RoF links [7]. So, when the optical transmission power remains constant regardless of M (*i.e.*, $P_o = 5$ dBm), the OSNR will be in the range of (0-10), (10-20), and (20-30) [dB] for $M = 64$, 32, and 16 RAUs, respectively. According to these results, the use of deeper modulation indexes are

Fig. 3. **Left-axis (blue):** OSNR as function of modulation index (β) for different numbers of RAUs (M) in the optical fronthaul. Circles: $M = 16$. Squares: $M = 32$. Diamonds: $M = 64$. Rest of the parameters are given in Table I. **Right-axis (red):** CR as function of the modulation index β .

Fig. 4. OSNR/SNR as function of the modulation index (β) for different RAU numbers (M). Circles: $M=16$. Squares: $M=32$. Diamonds: $M=64$. Rest of the parameters are given in Table I. OSNR values are included as references. Solid red lines: SNR (MS input). Dashed blue lines: OSNR (RAU input).

always recommended, at the expense of introducing non-linear distortion noise. For comparison, the CR that corresponds to each β is also included in Fig. 3 using a dashed red line.

The red solid lines of Fig. 4 show the received SNR at the MS for different values of β and M . For the sake of comparison, the OSNR curves at the input of the RAU, which represent the upper bound for the received SNR at the input of the MS, are also included for each case. From these curves, it is possible to see that the non-linear distortion that the optical fronthaul introduces has a more notable impact in those PON configuration with lower number of RAUs. As result of this, the gap that exists between the OSNR and SNR curves of each configuration grows with β assuming M fixed. The opposite situation takes place when β remains fixed and M grows (*i.e.*, the larger is M , the smaller is the OSNR-SNR gap).

Fig. 5. BER for QPSK as function of the received SNR. Black line with circles: Ideal response (no scaling/distortion). Red line with squares: CR = 20 dB. Green line with diamonds: CR = 15 dB. Blue line with down-pointing triangles: CR = 10 dB. Magenta line with up-pointing triangles: CR = 5 dB. Solid lines: Theoretical values. Point values ('*') were simulated.

Fig. 6. BER for 16-QAM as function of the received SNR. Black line with circles: Ideal response (no scaling/distortion). Red line with squares: CR = 20 dB. Green line with diamonds: CR = 15 dB. Blue line with down-pointing triangles: CR = 10 dB. Magenta line with up-pointing triangles: CR = 5 dB. Solid lines: Theoretical values. Point values ('*') were simulated.

As expected, there is an optimum value of β that maximizes the received SNR for each given fronthaul configuration.

Figures 5 and 6 show the Bit Error Rate (BER) that the MS experiences when QPSK and 16-QAM are used per subcarrier, respectively. The BER curves are presented as function of the SNR and CR of the received signal. In all cases, Maximum Likelihood (ML) detection is used in reception. Solid curves are obtained analytically using the α and σ_Y^2 derived in (36) and (38), along with the closed form approximation formula

$$\text{BER}_{\text{MQAM}}(\text{SNR}) \approx \frac{2}{\log_2(M_{\text{qam}})} \left(1 - \frac{1}{\sqrt{M_{\text{qam}}}}\right) \times \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{\frac{3}{2} \frac{\alpha^2 \text{SNR}}{(1 + \sigma_Y^2 \text{SNR})(M_{\text{qam}} - 1)}} \right) \quad (40)$$

Fig. 7. Required received SNR as function of the CR of the transmitted signal. Solid lines: QPSK. Dashed lines: 16-QAM. Circles: $\text{BER} = 10^{-1}$. Squares: $\text{BER} = 10^{-2}$. Diamonds: $\text{BER} = 10^{-3}$. Triangles: $\text{BER} = 10^{-4}$.

reported in [16], where M_{qam} is the number of symbols in the QAM modulation scheme and $\text{erfc}(\cdot)$ is the complementary error function [15]. Note that the quality of approximation (40) is tightest at high SNR. Simulation results, represented in dotted lines with points (*), are also included to validate the theoretical analysis presented in Section III. In all cases, the BER curves with ideal response (*i.e.*, $\alpha = 1$ and $\sigma_Y^2 = 0$) are included as baseline. When comparing these curves, it is possible to characterize the effect that the CR of the input signal (or equivalently, the intensity modulation index of the MZM) has on the BER of the system. As expected, there is an optimal CR value (for each QAM modulation scheme) that fulfills the target BER in reception with minimal SNR.

Finally, Fig. 7 shows the relation between CR and received SNR to achieve a target BER for a given QAM scheme. Here, the CR value that minimizes the received SNR for a target BER is easily observed for each case. With the aid of the closed form formulas derived in this paper, the parameters that should be used to configure the analog fronthaul of a our proposed C-RAN architecture can be now easily estimated.

V. CONCLUSION

The integration of optical and wireless transmission technologies will be critical to achieve the target goals that have been set for 5G. In practice, this implies ultra-dense deployments of small cells that coordinate their transmission jointly, without incurring on high processing delay and excessive implementation costs. The use of a C-RAN architecture that implements centralized processing and an analog fronthaul has notable advantages with respect to the digital fronthaul solutions considered so far. However, the transmission of analog radio signals over an optical fronthaul network introduces non-linear distortion, whose impact needs to be characterized. In this paper, we focused on the effect that the non-linear response of the MZM (*i.e.*, the external optical modulator of

the CBS) has on the E2E performance of the C-RAN. A theoretical model for the non-linear distortion that is generated was proposed and, through it, the impact that this impairment has on different figures of merit of the C-RAN was characterized. When compared to traditional RoF links, it is interesting to note that the use of *moderate* optical intensity modulation indexes is convenient if they are properly selected, such that the impact of the non-linear distortion that is introduced is compensated by the additional OSNR gain that is obtained.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partly funded by the Ministry of Science, Innovation, and Universities of Spain under Project TERESA-TEC2017-90093-C3-1-R (AEI/FEDER, UE), and by the Catalan government under Grant 2017 SGR 1479.

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